

SOLIDIFICATION BEHAVIOUR OF PLLA/nHA NANOCOMPOSITES

C. Delabarde, C.J.G. Plummer, P.-E. Bourban, J.-A.E. Månson
Laboratoire de Technologie des Composites et Polymères (LTC),
Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), CH-1015, Switzerland
claire.delabarde@epfl.ch

SUMMARY

PLLA crystallization rates increase with nHA content owing to increased nucleation, which compensates a decrease in spherulite growth rate, G , at 100 to 130 °C, and to suppression of the twin peak in $G(T)$ seen in pure PLLA, linked to a transition from the α phase to the disordered α' phase as T decreases. The decrease in $G(T)$ reflects an increase in viscosity, but nHA may also favour the α' phase, with consequences not only for the crystallization kinetics but also for resorption rates.

Keywords: PLLA, nanocomposites, crystallization, hydroxyapatite, bone tissue engineering.

INTRODUCTION

Although bone is a dynamic tissue, its unique ability to self-regenerate is limited to small-scale trauma, and bone grafts are often necessary in surgical operations to treat major bone loss caused by fracture or bone tumors (half a million bone grafts are performed annually in the United States alone). There is consequently growing interest in biodegradable synthetic scaffolds for bone repair and/or re-modelling [1]. The most widely used resorbable synthetic polymers for biomedical applications are saturated poly- α -hydroxy esters, such as poly(lactic acid), poly(glycolic acid) and poly(lactic-coglycolide) copolymers [2]. Our own work has focused on porous scaffolds prepared from Poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA), a semi-crystalline linear aliphatic polyester, which has found favor as a biomaterial over the last three decades thanks to its good mechanical properties and inherent biocompatibility. For this application, the PLLA is combined with a bioactive ceramic that promotes bone regeneration and osteointegration, i.e. nano-sized hydroxyapatite particles (nHA) ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) [3].

Such scaffolds must fulfil several specific requirements, including a controllable degradation rate, which should match that of bone tissue growth rate, in order to maintain the overall mechanical integrity of the system. PLLA readily undergoes hydrolytic degradation via de-esterification [4] at a rate that is known to be strongly dependent on its degree of crystallinity and crystalline morphology [5-8]. The crystalline modifications and crystallization kinetics of PLLA have been widely studied and there is strong evidence for a transition from an ordered orthorhombic α phase to a less ordered α' modification with decreasing crystallization temperature, T_c , which may account for the unusual double peak in the spherulite growth rate G as a function of T_c

[9, 10]. Recent work has also addressed the influence of nano-sized fillers on the crystallization of PLLA and related polymers. For example, Di *et al.* concluded that exfoliated organically modified clay platelets act as nucleating agents at low concentrations, but become crystallization retardants at high concentrations, owing to significant physical hindrance of molecular motion in the PLA [11], and similar conclusions were drawn by Wu *et al.* from studies of PLLA/clay nanocomposites [12]. In what follows, we consider the influence of the nHA on the development of crystalline morphology in PLLA. Not only resorption rates but also processing and physical properties are expected to be critically dependent extent of crystallization and the nature of the crystalline phase, and it is therefore important to understand the relationships between these different aspects of the materials performance in order to adapt processing conditions accordingly.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Specimen Preparation

Bioresorbable poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA, intrinsic viscosity 1.6 dL/g, nominal melting point, T_m , 181.7 °C from Boehringer Ingelheim, Germany), was provided in the form of flakes and dried overnight at 75 °C under vacuum prior to use. Hydroxyapatite nanopowder (nHA, mean diameter < 200 nm from BET analysis, Sigma-Aldrich) was used without further purification or thermal treatment.

PLLA and HA were melt mixed under dry nitrogen to limit PLLA degradation, using a miniextruder equipped with twin conical co-rotating screws and a capacity of 5 cm³ (DMS Micro 5 compounder, Netherlands). A screw rotation rate of 110 rpm, a temperature of 200 °C and a residence time of 4 min were used throughout. Compounds containing 0, 5 and 10 wt% of nHA were prepared under these conditions and subsequently stored at -18 °C.

Characterization

Specimens of PLLA/5 and 10 wt% nHA were embedded in epoxy resin and 80 nm sections prepared using an ultramicrotome (Reichert-Jung Ultracut-E) at ambient temperature with a diamond knife (Diatome). The sections were picked up on formvar/carbon covered 200 mesh copper grids and the nanoparticle dispersion observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Philips CM-20) at 200 kV.

Spherulite growth rates were determined by polarized light microscopy (Olympus BH2) equipped with a Linkam TMHS 600 hot stage. Approximately 0.3 mg of dried PLLA or PPLA/nHA was compressed between two microscope cover slips and placed on the hot stage. The specimen was maintained at 210 °C for 1 min and cooled at 50 K/min to the required temperature. G was then determined from linear least squares fits to the spherulite radii plotted as function of time, averaged over 10 independent measurements.

Specimens cut from 200 μm thick compression-molded sheets, crystallized using the hot stage under the same conditions as for the optical measurements, were investigated by wide angle X-Ray diffraction (XRD). In this case, crystallization was allowed to

terminate as determined by optical inspection and the films cooled to room temperature prior to the XRD scans, which were carried out in reflection using a PANalytical X'Pert Pro MPD diffractometer in the θ - θ configuration (Cu $K\alpha$, $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$).

The influence of nHA on the dynamic rheological properties of the specimens was studied using an Advanced Rheometric Expansion System (ARES) (Rheometrics Europe GmbH). The measurements were performed in dynamic oscillatory shear mode using 25 diameter parallel plates. Frequency sweeps from 0.1 to 100 rad/s were carried out on 1 mm thick, 25 mm diameter compression molded discs at 10 % strain, which is in the linear viscoelastic range.

Global solidification rates under isothermal conditions were determined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, TA Instruments Q100) under nitrogen. Circular specimens of approximately 3 mg in mass were cut from a 200 μm thick compression-molded sheet and placed in aluminum pan. They were held at 210 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 min to erase the effects of the prior thermal history, cooled at 80 K/min to the required crystallization temperature, and maintained at this temperature for three times the time corresponding to the peak in the crystallization exotherm. The specimens were then cooled to 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 80 K/min and reheated to 210 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 10 K/min, in order investigate the melting behavior.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows TEM images of thin sections taken from melt extruded PLLA/nHA nanocomposites containing 5 and 10 wt% nHA. Both images indicate a uniform dispersion of nanometric nHA particles (20 to 50 nm in diameter) although larger particles were also occasionally present.

Figure 1. TEM images of PLLA/nHA nanocomposites after melt extrusion: (a) PLLA/5 wt% nHA; (b) PLLA/10 wt% nHA.

Figure 2. Spherulite growth rates as a function of temperature for (a) pure PLLA, (b) PLLA/5 wt% nHA and (c) PLLA/10 wt% nHA; (d) optical micrograph of PLLA spherulites between crossed-polarizers ($T_c = 120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

G is shown in Figure 2 as a function of temperature for PLLA, PLLA/5 wt% nHA and PLLA/10 wt% nHA along with a representative optical micrograph of PLLA spherulites grown isothermally at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and observed between crossed polarizers. In the pure PLLA, $G(T)$ showed two maxima at approximately $105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a corresponding minimum at approximately $110\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, consistent with previous observations for PLLA [10, 13]. This contrasts with the bell-shaped curve typically observed in semicrystalline polymers, which derives from the competition between the thermodynamic driving force for spherulite, which increases with the degree of supercooling, $T_m^o - T_c$, where T_m^o is the equilibrium melting point, and the chain mobility, which decreases with decreasing T . At 5 wt% nHA, the absolute values of $G(T)$ were significantly lower than those for pure PLLA, particularly in the temperature range 100 to $130\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and the maximum in $G(T)$ at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was partly suppressed, although a maximum was still clearly visible at about $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Similar trends were seen in the data for PLLA/10 wt% nHA, but in this case the peak in $G(T)$ at about $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was more pronounced than for PLLA/5 wt% nHA, and the absolute values of $G(T)$ were somewhat greater at $T < 100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ than for both PLLA/5 wt% nHA and the pure PLLA.

Figure 3. XRD patterns for PLLA the corresponding nanocomposites: (a) $T_c = 105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; (b) $T_c = 115\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 4. Complex viscosity of PLLA for different weight fractions of nHA at $190\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

XRD data from specimens crystallized at $T_c = 105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $115\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ are shown in Figure 3. The most intense peak at $2\theta = 16.87\text{ }^\circ$ corresponded to the (200) and (110) reflections of the α modification of PLLA, and the peaks at 15.03 , 19.28 , 22.6 ° could be indexed (010), (203) and (015), respectively [10, 12]. Whereas all these peaks were clearly present for $T_c = 115\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the (203) and (015) peaks were extremely weak for $T_c = 105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in all the materials, consistent with the appearance of less ordered α' modification for $T_c < 110\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Since a transition from the α to the α' modification with decreasing T_c has been invoked to explain the double peak in $G(T)$, it may be significant that for $T_c = 115\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the (203) and (015) peaks were slightly weaker in the presence of nHA [10]. This may indicate preferential growth of the α' modification and hence account for the relatively high $G(T)$ in PLLA/10 wt% nHA at low T_c , in spite of the overall decrease in $G(T)$ observed at intermediate temperatures. This decrease in $G(T)$ may be explained in terms of a reduction in matrix mobility, particularly at low T , where the transport term dominates, consistent with Figure 4, which shows the complex viscosity, η^* , of pure PLLA, PLLA/5 wt% nHA and PLLA/10 wt% nHA at $190\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as a function of angular frequency, ω . A Newtonian plateau was observed between about 0.3 rad/s and 10 rad/s

for all the materials, but there was a significant increase in the absolute values of η^* with increasing nHA content, η^* more than doubling on addition of 5 wt% nHA. Similar trends were observed at lower T , although the onset of crystallization prevented precise measurements in the range corresponding directly to the T_c referred to above.

The relative crystallinity, $X_r(t)$, was defined from the DSC measurements as the ratio of the area under the exothermic peak after a crystallization time t , and the total area under exothermic peak:

$$X_r(t) = \frac{\int_0^t (dH/dt) dt}{\int_0^\infty (dH/dt) dt} \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

where dH/dt is the measured heat flow rate. Figure 5 summarizes the DSC data in the form of a time-temperature-transformation (TTT) diagram for $X_r = 50\%$ and $X_r = 95\%$ in the temperature range 90 to 130 °C. The “C” shape of the TTT curves reflects a maximum in crystallization rates at intermediate temperatures. There was a significant “kink” in the curves for pure PLLA between 110 and 120 °C, which may be imputed to the double peak in $G(T)$. Moreover, the addition of the nHA particles resulted in a significant increase in the crystallization rates as reflected by a shift in the curves to lower times, even though $G(T)$ was found to decrease over much of the temperature range considered.

Figure 5. Time-temperature-transformation diagram for PLLA and the corresponding nanocomposites for relative crystallinities, X_r , of 50 % and 95 %.

$X_r(t)$ may in principle be analysed using the Avrami equation:

$$X_r(t) = 1 - \exp(-Kt^n) \quad (\text{eq.2})$$

where n , the Avrami exponent, depends on mode of nucleation and the geometry of the growth process, and K , the Avrami rate constant, is related to the nucleation and growth rates [14]. For spherulites growing in three dimensions and instantaneous heterogeneous

nucleation at $t = 0$, $n = 3$ and $K = 3\pi G^3 N / 4$, where N is the number of nucleation sites per unit volume. In the present case, optical microscopy confirmed the assumption of heterogeneous nucleation to be a reasonable approximation over the range of temperatures in which the measurements of $G(T)$ were carried out. The film thicknesses of 200 μm used for the DSC measurements were greater than or equal to the maximum spherulite diameters observed optically, so that three-dimensional growth (as opposed to two dimensional growth) could also be assumed. At the highest T_c , where the spherulites were relatively large, truncation effects were nevertheless expected to be significant at the longest crystallization times. K values were determined on this basis by taking $n = 3$ and fitting eq.2 to the experimental $X_r(t)$ (eq.1). Figure 6 shows results plotted as a function of T_c . As may be anticipated from Figure 5, all the materials showed a peak in K in the neighborhood of 105 $^\circ\text{C}$, and K increased with increasing nHA content. Comparison of Figures 2 and 6 therefore indicates substantial increase in N in the presence of the nHA over the whole temperature range, consistent with a decrease in the mean spherulite diameters observed optically, and which presumably compensates the decreases in $G(T)$.

Figure 6. K as a function of crystallization temperature for PLLA and the corresponding nanocomposites.

As shown in Figure 7(a), addition of nHA resulted in little change in the melting temperatures, T_m , observed after isothermal crystallization at a given T_c . All the materials showed extensive structural modification during the DSC heating scans, as suggested by the DSC traces shown in Figure 7(b) for pure PLLA crystallized at 100 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ [13, 15]. For $T_c = 100$ $^\circ\text{C}$ the main endotherm was preceded by a clear exotherm, and T_m varied little with T_c in this temperature range, both of which may be attributed to a transformation from the α' to the α modification, as the temperature is raised [10]. For higher T_c , where the α modification is assumed to be increasingly dominant, a double endotherm was observed (cf. the trace for $T_c = 120$ $^\circ\text{C}$). In this case the lower temperature peak may be interpreted as corresponding to T_m for the lamellae initially present in the specimen (although it may also be influenced by the α' to α

transition), and the higher temperature peak is due to recrystallization. Application of the Hoffman-Weeks construction [16] to these T_m values (Figure 7(a)), suggested T_m^o to be about 200 °C for all the materials, consistent with literature results for pure PLLA [10, 12, 17], and hence that the low temperature peak is associated with the α phase in all the specimens crystallized at and above 110 °C. On the other hand, comparison of the DSC traces for PLLA, PLLA/5 wt% nHA and PLLA/10 wt% nHA crystallized at 115 °C (Figure 7(c)) indicated the area of the α melting peak to be considerably reduced with respect to that of the recrystallization peak in the presence of nHA, again suggesting that addition of nHA tends to promote the growth of the α' phase.

Figure 7. (a) DSC melting points, T_m , of PLLA and the corresponding nanocomposites as a function of T_c ; (b) DSC heating scans of PLLA after isothermal crystallization at 100 °C and 120 °C; (c) DSC heating scans of PLLA, PLLA/5 wt% nHA and PLLA/10 wt% nHA after isothermal crystallization at 115 °C.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study has provided evidence that nHA has a significant influence on the crystallization behaviour of PLLA. nHA particles were found to act as spherulite growth retardants at intermediate temperatures, consistent with an observed increase in melt viscosity in the presence of the nHA, although evidence was also provided for promotion of the disordered low temperature α' phase at high nHA contents. In spite of

the overall decrease in $G(T)$ on nHA addition, global crystallization rates, represented here in the form of TTT diagrams, increased substantially. Avrami analysis, based on the assumption of three-dimensional crystallization and heterogeneous nucleation, was used to demonstrate explicitly that this was due to an increase in N , as confirmed qualitatively by optical microscopy. The next stage of the investigation will be to study the influence of these factors on the resorption behaviour, which is known to be dependent on the degree of crystallinity [7, 8, 18], but is also expected to be influenced both by the degree of order of the crystalline phase and directly by the presence of the nHA, owing to both its relative hydrophilicity and hydrolytic degradation via the matrix/nanofiller interfaces [19, 20].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to acknowledge the technical support of the Interdisciplinary Center for Electron Microscopy (CIME) and the Laboratory of Biomechanical Orthopedics (LBO) of the EPFL, Dr. Cristian Neagu of the LTC-EPFL for helpful discussions, and the School of Engineering (STI) of the EPFL for financial support.

References

1. Rezwan, K., et al., *Biodegradable and bioactive porous polymer/inorganic composite scaffolds for bone tissue engineering*. *Biomaterials*, 2006. 27(18): p. 3413-3431.
2. Mano, J.f., et al., *Bioinert, biodegradable and injectable polymeric matrix composites for hard tissue replacement: State of the art and recent developments*. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2004. 64(6): p. 789-817.
3. Mathieu, L.M., et al., *Bioresorbable composites prepared by supercritical fluid foaming*. *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research - Part A*, 2005. 75(1): p. 89-97.
4. Gupta, B., N. Revagade, and J. Hilborn, *Poly(lactic acid) fiber: An overview*. *Progress in Polymer Science (Oxford)*, 2007. 32(4): p. 455-482.
5. Mainil-Varlet, P., B. Rahn, and S. Gogolewski, *Long-term in vivo degradation and bone reaction to various polylactides. 1. One-year results*. *Biomaterials*, 1997. 18(3): p. 257-266.
6. Walton, M. and N.J. Cotton, *Long-term in vivo degradation of poly-L-lactide (PLLA) in bone*. *Journal of Biomaterials Applications*, 2007. 21(4): p. 395-411.
7. Alexis, F., et al., *Some insight into hydrolytic scission mechanisms in bioerodible polyesters*. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 2006. 102(4): p. 3111-3117.
8. Tsuji, H. and Y. Ikada, *Properties and morphology of poly(L-lactide) 4. Effects of structural parameters on long-term hydrolysis of poly(L-lactide) in phosphate-buffered solution*. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 2000. 67(1): p. 179-189.
9. Zhang, J., et al., *Crystal modifications and thermal behavior of poly(L-lactic acid) revealed by infrared spectroscopy*. *Macromolecules*, 2005. 38(19): p. 8012-8021.

10. Pan, P., et al., *Polymorphous crystallization and multiple melting behavior of poly(L-lactide): Molecular weight dependence*. *Macromolecules*, 2007. 40(19): p. 6898-6905.
11. Di, Y., et al., *Poly(lactic acid)/organoclay nanocomposites: Thermal, rheological properties and foam processing*. *Journal of Polymer Science, Part B: Polymer Physics*, 2005. 43(6): p. 689-698.
12. Wu, D., et al., *Comparison between isothermal cold and melt crystallization of polylactide/clay nanocomposites*. *Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology*, 2008. 8(4): p. 1658-1668.
13. Di Lorenzo, M.L., *The crystallization and melting processes of poly(L-lactic acid)*. *Macromolecular Symposia*, 2006. 234: p. 176-183.
14. Avrami, M., *Kinetics of phase change. I: General theory*. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 1939. 7(12): p. 1103-1112.
15. Park, J.W. and S.S. Im, *Morphological changes during heating in poly(L-lactic acid)/poly(butylene succinate) blend systems as studied by synchrotron X-ray scattering*. *Journal of Polymer Science, Part B: Polymer Physics*, 2002. 40(17): p. 1931-1939.
16. Huffman, J.D. and J.J. Weeks, *Rate of spherulitic crystallization with chain folds in polychlorotrifluoroethylene*. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 1962. 37(8): p. 1723-1741.
17. Kalb, B. and A.J. Pennings, *General crystallization behaviour of poly(l-lactic acid)*. *Polymer*, 1980. 21(6): p. 607-612.
18. Renouf-Glauser, A.C., et al., *A degradation study of PLLA containing lauric acid*. *Biomaterials*, 2005. 26(15): p. 2415-2422.
19. Paul, M.A., et al., *Polylactide/montmorillonite nanocomposites: Study of the hydrolytic degradation*. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 2005. 87(3): p. 535-542.
20. Zhou, Q. and M. Xanthos, *Nanoclay and crystallinity effects on the hydrolytic degradation of polylactides*. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 2008. 93(8): p. 1450-1459.